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Medical Sciences

Vascular anal pathology in patients with obesity, confirmed by the results of outpatient sigmoidoscopy and anoscopy. Morbidity and statistics of operations

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We analyzed the attendance of clinics in the republic, the prevalence of the diagnosis of vascular anal pathology in obese patients (hemorrhoidal disease), confirmed by medical examination (results of outpatient sigmoidoscopy and anoscopy).

Statistical data taken from medical organizations located in various regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan was used.

Taking into account open medical republican data, an analysis of cases of diseases and requests of patients for medical help was carried out. The prevalence of hemorrhoids in the Republic of Kazakhstan was determined using official statistics from medical organizations. The results obtained indicate that the leaders in the proportion of patients who were operated on for hemorrhoids among the population of the republic are three regions. These are the North Kazakhstan region (16.3%), the East Kazakhstan region (11.3%), and the city of Astana (10.6%).

Figure 1. Regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan with a high incidence of hemorrhoidectomy

In terms of the proportion of patients with hemorrhoidal disease, Astana is the second indicator in the country after the Turkestan region. The figure is about 15.3%, versus 15.7% (according to data published in 2023). This is quite consistent with previous studies over a 5-year period and the results of some international data. At the same time, in terms of the share of visits from people suffering from obesity and hemorrhoids, the city of Astana was in first place (in the lead). Therefore, we studied the statistics of patients with hemorrhoids and hemorrhoidectomy in order to find out what proportion of the population falls into various degrees of obesity.

Materials and methods

The study carried out a retrospective and prospective analysis of medical records of patients diagnosed with stage I-IV hemorrhoids who were treated at the clinical bases of a medical university (Astana).

The study selected patients with hemorrhoidal disease who were overweight and obese. The information collection period is 5 years (2018-2023). Patients with hemorrhoidal disease (HD) underwent surgical treatment both in a surgical hospital and on an outpatient basis. Indications for surgical treatment were generally accepted recommendations and protocols for surgical treatment of a chronic disease (stage 3-4 hemorrhoids).

To analyze clinical material, correctly formulate a diagnosis, and a universal approach to determining indications for surgery, the Goligher classification was used, in which Stage 1 is bleeding hemorrhoids; Stage 2- hemorrhoids with bleeding and protrusion, with spontaneous reduction; Stage 3- hemorrhoids with bleeding and protrusion, which requires manual reduction; Stage 4, hemorrhoids with prolapse that cannot be reduced.

The category of overweight included patients with a body mass index (BMI) up to 30 kg/m² or 25-29.9 kg/m².

Patients with the following BMI indicators were selected into the category of obese individuals, ranked into 5 degrees:

BMI=30 < 35 kg/m² (I degree obesity);

BMI=35 < 40 kg/m² (II degree obesity);

BMI=40 < 50 kg/m² (III degree obesity);

BMI=50 < 60 kg/m² (Obesity IV, which corresponds to the previously used term “Super Obese”);

BMI 60 < 70 kg/m² (Obesity V, which corresponds to the previously used term “Super Obese”. results We studied the databases of patients who were registered in public and private clinics. And who had a medical certificate “hemorrhoidal disease”.

Surgeries to remove hemorrhoids were performed in the clinic at the “Ambulatory Surgery Centers”, which adhere to the principle of “one-day surgery”. And also in outpatient day hospitals, where the patient after surgery can be under the supervision of medical personnel during the day (until the evening). And in the evening they go to spend the night at home.

Hospitalization and surgical treatment were carried out for persons suffering from concomitant or comorbid pathology. Including patients with symptoms of subcompensation, or who had a history of certain complications of hemorrhoidal disease (for example, bleeding), etc.

The proportion of patients with stage I obesity who received surgical treatment for hemorrhoidal disease was 32.3%

The proportion of patients with stage II obesity who received surgical treatment for hemorrhoidal disease was 17.2%

The proportion of patients with grade III obesity who received surgical treatment for hemorrhoidal disease was 28.1%

The proportion of patients with stage IV obesity who received surgical care for hemorrhoidal disease was 19.0%

The proportion of patients with stage V obesity who received surgical treatment for hemorrhoidal disease was 3.4%.

The results are presented graphically in the form of a diagram with a polynomial trend line (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Prevalence of hemorrhoidal disease (hemorrhoidectomy) in obese patients

It should be noted that the rate of medical and surgical care (for the treatment of hemorrhoidal disease) in patients with obesity of IV and V degree to the clinic is quite high. Higher than in patients with obesity of I, II and III degrees. However, the number of operations in persons with a BMI of $60 < 70 \text{ kg/m}^2$ (Class V obesity) is extremely small. To a greater extent, due to the caution of coloproctologists, who diagnosed an extremely high risk of surgery and preferred to treat such patients conservatively.

Discussion of the results obtained

All of the above statistical indicators were typical for the city of Astana. That said, we believe that this study has some limitations. The reasons for this are that not all city data are taken into account. They can also be somewhat subjective due to a lack of information from smaller clinics and outpatient medical offices. And also from those specialists who did not confirm their participation in the study.

Although our results are quite consistent with previous studies over a 5-year period and the results of some international data.

Conclusions.

To determine the true picture of morbidity in the republic, the number of complications of hemorrhoidal disease before and after hemorrhoidectomy (in all regions), a large-scale epidemiological study is necessary. An urgent problem is the development of methods of prevention and increasing the detection of hemorrhoids in the population in the early stages of its development.

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